

Supplementary Material

Cold Chain Resilience Across Humanitarian and Resource-Constrained Settings: A Hybrid Simulation Framework

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S1. Spoilage Models

Supplementary Figure S1. Behaviors of different spoilage models across sensitive, medium, and tolerant items.

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S2. Intervention Parameter Adjustments

Supplementary Table S1. Parameter modifications for Gaza conflict-affected setting interventions.

Intervention	Parameter	Updated Value
Power Upgrade	Battery capacity (Wh)	8000
	Solar efficiency	0.85
	Charge efficiency	0.95
	Discharge efficiency	0.98
	Generator output (W)	4000
	Fuel capacity (L)	40
	Fuel usage (L/h)	0.7
Behavior Change	Misuse profile	Careful
	Door interval (s)	240
	Open duration (min)	1
	Agent training	Enabled
Resilient Grid	Sabotage chance	0.002
	Grid uptime	0.9
	Blackout chance	0.0001
	Blackout hours	22–23, 8–9
	Repair delay chance	0.01
Fridge Upgrade	Fridge insulation (R-value)	6
	Clinic cooling power (W)	200
	Depot cooling power (W)	300
	Warehouse cooling power (W)	600
	Thermal mass (J/K)	10000
	Initial temperature (°C)	3

Supplementary Table S2. Parameter modifications for Sudan rural conflict-affected setting interventions.

Intervention	Parameter	Updated Value
Power Upgrade	Battery capacity (Wh)	10000
	Solar efficiency	0.80
	Solar panel area (m ²)	40
	Charge efficiency	0.96
	Discharge efficiency	0.97
	Generator output (W)	3000
	Fuel capacity (L)	50
	Fuel usage (L/h)	0.6
Fridge Upgrade	Fridge insulation (R-value)	6
	Clinic cooling power (W)	150
	Depot cooling power (W)	250
	Warehouse cooling power (W)	350
	Thermal mass (J/K)	8000
	Initial temperature (°C)	3
Robust Transport	Transport insulation (R-value)	3.0
	Transport delay chance	0.02
	Icepack mass (kg)	4.0
	Box volume (L)	25
	Initial temperature (°C)	3
	Looting chance	0.0005
	Roadblock chance	0.001

Supplementary Table S3. Parameter modifications for Nepal highlands setting interventions.

Intervention	Parameter	Updated Value
Warm Chain	Min temp override (°C)	2
	Max temp override (°C)	12
	Misuse profile	Careful
	Door interval (s)	300
	Open duration (min)	1
Route Improved	Transport delay chance	0.002
	Roadblock chance	0.002
	Looting chance	0.0005
	Repair delay chance	0.001
Container Upgrade	Transport insulation (R-value)	3.5
	Icepack mass (kg)	5.0
	Box volume (L)	30
	Initial temperature (°C)	3

Supplementary Table S4. Parameter modifications for Haiti post-earthquake setting interventions.

Intervention	Parameter	Updated Value
Power Hardening	Battery capacity (Wh)	8000
	Solar efficiency	0.70
	Solar peak output (W)	700
	Charge efficiency	0.97
	Discharge efficiency	0.98
	Generator output (W)	3500
	Fuel capacity (L)	60
	Fuel usage (L/h)	0.5
Mobile Units	Transport insulation (R-value)	3.2
	Box volume (L)	25
	Icepack mass (kg)	4.5
	Initial temperature (°C)	3
	Passive transport mode	Enabled
Infrastructure Shockproofing	Repair delay chance	0.01
	Grid uptime	0.6
	Blackout chance	0.25
	Sabotage chance	0.001
	Battery theft chance	0.005
Community Training	Misuse profile	Careful
	Tampering chance	0.005
	Agent training	Enabled
	Door interval (s)	240
	Open duration (min)	1

S3. Power System Utilization Across Scenarios

Supplementary Figure S2. Power utilization for Gaza clinic 1.

Supplementary Figure S3. Power utilization for Sudan depot 1.

Supplementary Figure S4. Power utilization for Haiti warehouse 1.